

Data-driven approach for assessing ventilation thermal performance based on main heat meter readings

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Abstract. The significance of energy management and optimization in modern building operations cannot be overstated. However, many buildings lack the necessary connectivity, leading to underutilized metered data and possible inefficiencies. This study develops a data-driven method to assess ventilation system thermal performance using main heat meter readings, clustering techniques, and identifying distinct heat use profiles on a scale of a day. The main hypothesis of this research is that in inefficient systems, especially during warmer periods, the total heat use change mirrors the heat consumed by ventilation systems. Conducted on 6 university buildings, our findings revealed that during transitional periods, such as mornings and evenings, ventilation systems significantly influence heat use. In buildings with less efficient heat exchangers or suboptimal setpoints, this impact was clearer. These results provide actionable insights for building operators and contribute to the conversation on data-driven energy efficiency in building management.

1 Introduction

Modern methodologies in HVAC (Heating, Ventilation and Air Conditioning) optimization are increasingly incorporating data-driven approaches, using advanced technologies and machine learning algorithms to enhance systems' efficiency and indoor comfort. The research domain focuses on estimating parameters such as temperature, airflow, and occupancy levels, utilizing various data sources like building management systems, historical sensor data, and user feedback [1-8].

However, real-world existing buildings often lack advanced metering equipment. This is due to a variety of factors: the complexity and diversity of building types, which makes standardizing data collection challenging; the variability in the age and technology of buildings, with many older structures not equipped for modern metering; privacy concerns. These challenges make comprehensive energy data collection and efficient energy management in buildings more difficult compared to sectors like industry and transportation [9]. Nevertheless, the landscape is changing due to new policies making the installation of smart energy meters mandatory across the EU, to enhance energy efficiency and to meet the climate goals [10].

Addressing this gap, this study explores the possibility of initiating ventilation systems' optimization during warmer periods (with outdoor temperatures above freezing), using available data such as main heat meter readings, ventilation systems descriptions from construction projects, operational

schedules and setpoints. A significant point here is understanding the correlation between the total heat use and the efficiency of ventilation systems. The inefficiencies reveal themselves in systems with less efficient heat exchangers, where the unused thermal potential of exhaust air leads to additional heat use, and in cases of suboptimal inlet air setpoints, which may be higher than necessary, again increasing additional heat consumption.

Such exploratory approach sets the stage for a further detailed analysis, aiming to bridge the theoretical models with practical application and providing actionable insights for effective, data-driven ventilation thermal performance optimization, considering the real-world limitations of existing buildings.

2 Methods

In this method the building's heat use profiles throughout a day are identified via clustering and the within cluster energy use changes are then compared to theoretical additional ventilation systems' heat use. The additional heat use is computed depending on the outdoor air temperature and systems' supply air temperatures setpoints.

The application of clustering techniques offers an advantage in this analysis as it does not require pre-labelled data, which is often unavailable. Clustering allows grouping of datapoints based on their similarities, revealing potential relationships within the data that

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might not be immediately apparent. This approach allows us to identify unique heat use profiles and their segments that could be overlooked by methods dependent on predefined categories or labels.

The method is based on building main heat meter hourly readings, date and time values, weather data as well as information about buildings' ventilation systems. The systems' information includes number of ventilation systems, dimensioned air flow rate and each system's air handling unit's (AHU) heat exchanger temperature efficiency coefficients.

The method validation is based on building main heat meter hourly readings, identified clusters' centroids information, date and time values, and building ventilation heat use sub-meter hourly readings. The sub-meter logs are assigned to previously identified clusters and the within cluster energy use change is computed. The main heat meter changes are then compared to sub-meter changes.

The buildings (**Table 1**) in focus are from TalTech campus and combine office spaces, classrooms, auditoriums, and laboratories. Some buildings include kitchen space and dining areas.

Table 1. The buildings in focus

Building abbreviation	Building service area, m ²
LIB	11062
SOC	10360
SCI	6991
ICT	11413
MEK	4434
CON	3411

2.1 Description of the data

As the method aims to analyse heat use behaviour on the scale of a day, the meters' readings as well as weather data must be of hourly granularity. The heat use data is obtained from university buildings' management system (BMS). The BMS also serves as the primary source for obtaining detailed information on the operational rates and schedules of the ventilation systems. The characteristics of the systems, on the other hand, are gathered from the building projects' documentation. The weather data includes mean outdoor air temperature of each hour in Tallinn, Estonia.

For a better understanding of heat use patterns, the data is covering a period of a year, the start and end points depend on data availability. The period in this case is set to 01.11.2022 – 31.10.2023.

2.2 Heat use profiles

The clustering in the study is conducted using variables correlated with heat use profiles, rather than direct readings of energy use. This ensures that the identified clusters reflect operational patterns applicable to similar buildings in the area, independent to their specific energy use rate.

2.2.1 Input features

The chosen independent variables that could be linked with distinct periods of the day and corresponding energy use patterns are hour of the day, day type and outdoor air temperature values. The hour of the day is represented via two components – sine and cosine to represent the cyclic nature of time (1), the day type represents the division into workdays or the weekends, which also include public holidays.

$$\sin\left(\frac{2\pi h}{24}\right), \cos\left(\frac{2\pi h}{24}\right) \quad (1)$$

Additionally, before passing the features down to the clustering algorithm, it is important to scale them. This step ensures that variables with larger range do not influence the clustering results. The independent variables are scaled using Z-score scaler by applying a function from the scikit-learn library named StandardScaler. The function (2) standardizes features by removing the mean μ from each variable x and scaling it to unit variance σ [11].

$$Z = \frac{(x - \mu)}{\sigma} \quad (2)$$

2.2.2 Clustering

For the clustering step in the analysis, K-Means algorithm is utilized, a widely spread general-purpose clustering algorithm. It is chosen for its simplicity and suitability for the task. The clustering is implemented using KMeans function from the scikit-learn python library. The function computes and minimizes the sum of squared Euclidean distances between the points and their respective centroids, which is expressed as the inertia [11, 12]. In the equation (3), x_i represents one of the points, μ_j is the centroid of the j -th cluster, and C is the set of all clusters' centroids:

$$Inertia = \sum_{i=0}^n \min_{\mu_j \in C} (\|x_i - \mu_j\|^2) \quad (3)$$

Initiation of clustering requires a pre-set parameter - number of clusters. The optimal number of clusters is determined by evaluating the sum of errors (SSE) (4) across different cluster number, ranging from 1 to 10. The SSE is used to identify a point after which increasing the number of clusters does not result in a significant decrease in error. This evaluation is done algorithmically using the KneeLocator function from kneed python library, which detects the elbow point in the SSE values [9, 10]. The identified optimal number of clusters is then used when training the K-Means model.

$$SSE = \sum_{i=0}^n (x_i - \mu_{c(i)})^2, \quad (4)$$

where n is the number of data points, x_i represents each data point, $\mu_{c(i)}$ is the centroid of the cluster.

2.2.3 Identification of heat use profiles

After the clustering step, features distribution plots for each cluster are used to evaluate the results. The heat use readings are assigned to the respective cluster based on the date and time.

2.3 Exploring heat use changes

The change in heat use within each cluster is determined using the range of values for each day the cluster appears in. This is done by finding the difference between the minimum and maximum heat use readings within the cluster for that day. For the further analysis, the average outdoor air temperature of the same period is computed (the period of each cluster in each day).

2.3.1 Comparison

The within cluster total heat use change is analysed by comparing the values to ventilation systems' theoretical additional heat use. The ventilation additional heat use is computed considering the changes in operational level of each system, each system's AHU heat exchanger temperature efficiency coefficient and supply air temperature setpoint.

In order to prepare for this calculation, the operational rate of each ventilation system and their respective share of the building's total airflow for each hour across the entire observation period have to be determined. The process proceeds as follows:

1. Calculate daily within-cluster change: For each system, the daily changes in the airflow within each cluster are computed.
2. Compute mean within-cluster change: These daily changes across all days associated with each cluster are aggregated to find the average change in the airflows. These average values represent the typical variations in the systems.

Using these mean within-cluster airflow changes for each system, the theoretical additional heat use for each ventilation system can be estimated. Yet, one assumption must be made – the extract air temperature. The calculation takes place for several extract air temperature values, depending on the supply air setpoint temperature: the same as supply air setpoint temperature, 2 and 4 °C higher than the setpoint temperature.

Table 2. Overview of ventilation systems' characteristics

Building	Normalised Airflow Rate	HEX type			HEX efficiency
		Rotary	Plate	Run around coil	
-	L/s m ²	-	-	-	%
LIB	1.6	8	2	-	68.5
SOC	2.5	3	-	2	58.6
SCI	4.8	3	-	3	54.8
ICT	1.3	2	-	3	63.9
MEK	2.9	5	-	1	60.7
CON	2.5	2	2	-	75.4

The additional heat use by each AHU is calculated by firstly finding the temperature of air after passing the heat exchanger in the AHU (t_{HEX}), considering the exchange efficiency (η) and whether it is in a heating or cooling mode, based on the setpoint temperature (t_{sp}) relative to outdoor air temperature (t_{out}) (5).

$$t_{HEX} [^{\circ}C] = \begin{cases} t_{out} + \eta \cdot (t_{ex} - t_{out}), & t_{sp} > t_{out} \\ t_{ex} - \eta \cdot (t_{ex} - t_{out}), & t_{sp} \leq t_{out} \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

Secondly, the additional heat required to bring the supply air closer to the setpoint is calculated using airflow change, accounting for 1-degree increase while passing through the supply ventilator.

Additional validation step included applying the same method and identified clusters to building's ventilation systems' heat use sub-meter readings and evaluating the correlation, using the Pearson correlation coefficient within identified clusters.

2.4 Limitations

There are several limitations in this study, not all the mentioned buildings could have been overviewed and analysed at the same level, as some information was not available. Several buildings lacked enough project documentation and systems schedules in the BMS, limiting the possibility to compute theoretical ventilation heat use.

3 Results

3.1 Buildings ventilation data

The process of collecting and preparing building data provided insights into the ventilation systems of these buildings. **Table 2** presents an overview of the systems' characteristics based on project documentations.

Additionally, information about the systems' configurations was obtained, including operational schedules and supply air setpoint temperatures (**Table 3**). **Fig. 1** illustrates the operational rates of the ventilation systems across several buildings during workdays. This operational level was calculated by evaluating the operational settings of each system for every hour of the day, along with the proportion of the building's total airflow managed by each system during those hours. The plot also indicates variations in the operational rates throughout the workweek, helping to identify peak usage times.

The SCI building ventilation system operates near full capacity consistently, likely due to several laboratory floors in the building. In comparison, the CON building's ventilation schedule is different from those of the LIB and SOC buildings, likely due to its recent construction and more modern operational settings.

Table 3. Overview of supply air temperature setpoints

Building	Temperature setpoint, °C		
	Minimum	Average	Maximum
LIB	15.0	19.5	22.0
SOC	19.7	20.9	22.0
SCI	19.0	20.4	21.5
CON	18.0	20.3	23.0

Fig. 1 Ventilation systems' operation levels on a weekday.

One key observation is that significant change in system operations occurred around traditional workday: near 5AM and 8PM. These time periods are the reference points when analysing total heat use data.

3.2 Clustering results

The clustering analysis was conducted on an hourly dataset covering the period from 01 November 2022 to 31 October 2023. This analysis was based solely on the hour of the day, the type of the day (weekday or weekend/public holiday), and outdoor air temperature. The goal was to identify distinct time-based clusters without the influence of heat use data, ensuring an unbiased categorisation of time periods.

As it is shown in **Fig. 2** and **Fig. 3**, four distinct clusters emerged from the data, each representing unique operational periods within the buildings throughout the year. These clusters were then labelled according to their primary characteristics (Table 4).

Fig. 2 shows the distribution of clusters at each hour across all days, illustrating predominant time periods where each cluster is most occurring. **Fig. 3** extends the distribution across the days of the week, showing how clusters' appearing varies with the weekly cycle.

Fig. 2. Clusters distribution by hour across the entire period.

Fig. 3. Clusters distribution throughout the week across the entire period.

Table 4. Cluster labels.

Cluster	Label
0	Workdays, Evening and Night-time
1	Workdays, Early Morning
2	Workdays, Office Hours
3	Weekend Activity

Particularly two of the clusters, labelled as Workdays, Early Morning and Workdays, Evening to Night-time, align closely with the periods marking the beginning and end of a typical workday. Additionally, we overlaid the actual heat use onto the temporal clusters to evaluate patterns in energy use (**Fig. 4**)

Fig. 4. Example heat use profiles segments by cluster.

These clusters: Workdays, Early Morning and Workdays, Evening to Night-time, demonstrated notable shifts in total heat use, corresponding to times when adjustments in the operational rates of ventilations systems are most likely to occur, as was also shown in **Fig. 1**.

This clustering effectively captured the periods of different activity within the buildings and provided a base for analysing the impact of ventilation systems' operations on total heat use.

3.3 Intra-cluster changes

3.3.1 Theoretical additional heat use

The additional theoretical heat use of the AHU-s was quantified for total heat use cluster-based changes evaluation. The additional heat use by the ventilation systems was identified by integrating hourly operational

rates and airflow shares of each system. The calculations considered the efficiency of heat exchange process and the setpoint temperatures for each system. The computed energy was aggregated by building and normalised to building service area.

The following **Fig. 5** shows within cluster heat use changes as well as theoretical AHU heat use in the buildings, for which the ventilation systems information was available.

Fig. 5. Within-cluster changes overview with ventilation systems' additional heat use, overview

When evaluating the figures, attention should be directed towards the slope of the increases and differences between metered data and the theoretical AHU heat use. Such comparison reveals whether the changes in total consumption are ventilation caused or if other factors are influencing total heat use at those times.

The assessment of heat use changes across the clusters revealed a clear pattern particularly during transitional periods of the mornings and the evenings. These times align with shifts in ventilation system operation, mirroring the trend of increased heat use as outdoor air temperatures decrease. This observation is particularly pronounced in the LIB and SOC buildings, where the theoretical heat AHU heat use models closely track the observed changes.

During work hours, the data presents a more complex picture, with scattered changes that seem less dependent on outdoor temperature variations, suggesting internal heat loads as a primary influence. The weekend activity cluster, spanning across 48 hours, shows the variability of the heat use across these days with outdoor air temperatures correlation.

In the SCI and CON buildings, the divergence between theoretical and observed heat use changes is more noticeable. The SCI building, with its constant indoor climate due to laboratory floors, suggests multiple factors influencing heat use. The CON building's results, during the office hours in particular, imply that heat use variations are primarily driven by ventilations systems operations, as indicated by submeter readings.

In the SOC building, the sharp increase in heat use changes of the approximately the same range as the theoretical AHU heat use, despite positive outdoor temperatures raises questions. Given the building's heat exchanger efficiencies and inlet air setpoints that do not take into account the possibility to use the indoor heat gains, it draws attention to potential inefficiencies and opportunities for optimization.

The SOC building's significant heat use increase, mirroring the theoretical AHU heat use even during positive outdoor temperature periods, raises questions about potential inefficiencies.

3.3.2 Main heat meter and ventilation sub-meter

For validation purposes, a comparison was conducted between metered readings from ventilation sub-systems and main heat meters, focusing specifically on changes within each cluster. However, due to limitations in data availability, only two buildings were evaluated in this analysis. Furthermore, one of these buildings had data available for only a three-month period.

The following **Fig. 6** shows the relationship between the within-cluster changes coming from both abovementioned sources. Correlation coefficient ρ values are added to each subplot for relationships additional description. The data presented in the figures covers the period of positive outdoor air temperatures.

Fig. 6. Correlation of total heat use to AHU heat use changes during periods with non-freezing outdoor temperatures

In both buildings analysed, the correlation coefficients in the workday morning and evening clusters were around 0.7. The periods with these moderate correlations aligned with expected changes in AHU operations, suggesting that the total heat use changes were ventilation influenced to some extent.

4 Discussion

In our study, which examined the thermal performance of ventilation systems in university buildings, we identified patterns in heat use changes linked to the operations of those systems. This was achieved using clustering as a key step, where the clusters were formed based on variables correlated with heat use, instead of relying only on energy use readings. The methodology and resulting clusters, therefore, have the potential to be applicable to other building types, particularly those with similar operating hours, such as offices and commercial buildings, and for buildings where ventilation systems operate on fixed schedules. This suggests that our findings could extend to a wider range of buildings where operational schedules of ventilation systems are available.

The increased heat use during morning, matching with ventilation activities, and the evening decrease suggest ventilation operations significantly impact energy use, regardless of AHU efficiency. However, despite the general influence of the ventilation systems, we observed cases indicating inefficiencies, possibly from outdated heat exchangers or suboptimal setpoint temperatures, as supported by variations between the theoretical heat use and the actual heat use changes.

While our method identified potential areas of focus, it did not point out specific issues. This highlights the importance of conducting further, more detailed analysis. This study underlined the importance of considering individual system characteristic separately and the influence of day night operation settings on total heat use, especially in morning transitions. Additionally, varying air volume ventilation systems could be observed separately.

For future research, we suggest a mixed approach that combines simulations, data-driven methods, and disaggregation of main heat meter readings. This approach is especially appropriate in scenarios where buildings lack advanced metering infrastructure. Such methodology will allow a more complete understanding of ventilation systems thermal performance, highlighting opportunities for adjustments that could significantly improve efficiency. We assume that these insights will drive more focused research in building management, leading the conversating towards more precise and practical strategies for monitoring and optimizing energy use in buildings.

5 Conclusion

Our study on ventilation systems thermal performance in university buildings reveals insights into the

dynamics of heat use in relation to ventilation operations. The analysis highlights the influence of ventilation systems, during morning periods, and points to inefficiencies in some buildings due to the factors like outdated heat exchangers or suboptimal setpoint temperatures. These findings support the importance of a more detailed approach to ventilation systems optimization, adjusted to each building's specific characteristics and usage patterns.

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